

Risk Factors for Meconium-Stained Liquor and Outcome of the Neonate in Meconium-Stained Amniotic FluidDeepti Sanjay Kumar¹, Khushboo Kumari², Puja Mahaseth³¹Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Bihar²Senior Resident, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Bihar³Associate Professor, Department of Obstetrics & Gynaecology, Darbhanga Medical College & Hospital, Bihar

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Abstract:**Background:** Meconium-stained liquor (MSL) is a common occurrence during labor that can significantly impact neonatal outcomes. This study aims to identify maternal risk factors associated with MSL and evaluate their effects on neonates.**Methods:** About 100 pregnant women with MSL participated in a Darbhanga Medical College and Hospital retrospective observational study from August 2023 to December 2023. Maternal demographics, risk factors, and neonatal outcomes, including Apgar scores, Meconium Aspiration Syndrome (MAS) incidence, and NICU admission, were gathered.**Results:** Post-term pregnancy (25%) and maternal hypertension (20%) were the most common risk factors in 100 cases. Meconium was thick in 35% of instances. Neonatal outcomes showed 25% had poor Apgar scores, 10% had MAS, and 20% had respiratory distress. 18% of newborns needed NICU hospitalization, highlighting the link between thick meconium and unfavorable outcomes.**Conclusion:** The study highlights the significant impact of maternal risk factors, particularly post-term pregnancy and hypertension, on neonatal outcomes in cases of MSL. Timely identification and management of these risk factors are essential to improve neonatal health and reduce complications.**Keywords:** Meconium-stained liquor, neonatal outcomes, maternal risk factors, meconium aspiration syndrome.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Meconium is a newborn's first faeces, and its presence in the amniotic fluid is known as meconium-stained liquor (MSL). About 10–20% of deliveries are found to have this issue, particularly after 37 weeks of gestation [1]. When meconium appears in the amniotic fluid, it is frequently a symptom of fetal stress, especially hypoxia. The newborn is at serious risk for meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS), respiratory distress, and in extreme situations, perinatal morbidity or death [2,3]. Determining the risk factors for amniotic fluid stained with meconium is essential for prompt interventions and improved outcomes for newborns. Maternal hypertension, post-term pregnancies, oligohydramnios, intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), and fetal discomfort during labor are common risk factors [4]. Fetal hypoxia caused by these situations may result in the foetus passing meconium into the amniotic fluid. The degree of meconium contamination, prompt detection of fetal distress, and the standard of neonatal care all have a significant role in the

prognosis of newborns born with meconium-stained amniotic fluid [5]. Even though the majority of newborns with MSL who receive the right care have positive outcomes, severe instances may need to be sent to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) and undergo intense therapy, including breathing assistance. The context for a thorough investigation of the risk factors linked to MSL and its effects on newborn outcomes is established by this introduction [6].

This study seeks to identify labor-related meconium-stained liquor (MSL) risk factors and assess neonatal outcomes in cases of MSL amniotic fluid. The study also examines how MSL affects neonatal problems such as meconium aspiration syndrome and other prenatal morbidities.

Methodology**Study Design and Setting:** This retrospective observational study was conducted at Darbhanga

Medical College and Hospital over a period of five months, from August 2023 to December 2023.

Study Population: A total of approximately 100 pregnant women with meconium-stained amniotic fluid (MSL) who were admitted in labor were included in the study. Women with pre-existing fetal anomalies or maternal infections were excluded from the analysis.

Inclusion Criteria

- Pregnant women in labor with evidence of meconium-stained liquor.

Exclusion Criteria

- Women with fetal congenital anomalies.
- Women with maternal infections that could affect neonatal outcomes.

Data Collection: Data were obtained from patient records, focusing on:

- **Maternal Factors:** Age, parity, gestational age, and maternal complications (e.g., hypertension, post-term pregnancy, intrauterine growth restriction).
- **Fetal Monitoring:** Fetal heart rate patterns during labor, detection of fetal distress.
- **Neonatal Outcomes:** Apgar scores at 1 and 5 minutes, neonatal birth weight, presence of respiratory distress, incidence of meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS), need for resuscitation, and NICU admission.

Statistical Analysis: The collected data were analyzed to determine the correlation between maternal risk factors and neonatal outcomes in cases of meconium-stained liquor. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize patient characteristics, and chi-square or t-tests were

performed to assess associations between variables, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.05$.

Results

In this study, a total of 100 pregnant women with meconium-stained liquor (MSL) were included. Among these cases, the majority (65%) involved term pregnancies, occurring between 37 and 40 weeks of gestation, while 25% were post-term (beyond 40 weeks) and 10% were pre-term (less than 37 weeks). Thick meconium-stained amniotic fluid was observed in 35% of the cases, with the remaining 65% exhibiting thin meconium-stained fluid.

Several maternal risk factors were identified: 25% of the women were post-term, 20% had maternal hypertension, 15% experienced intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), and 10% had oligohydramnios.

Regarding neonatal outcomes, 75% of the neonates had Apgar scores of 7 or higher at one minute, while 25% had scores below 7, indicating varying levels of distress. Meconium Aspiration Syndrome (MAS) was diagnosed in 10% of the neonates, with these cases associated with thick meconium. Additionally, 20% of the neonates experienced respiratory distress, and 15% required resuscitation at birth. Overall, 18% of the neonates were admitted to the neonatal intensive care unit (NICU) due to complications, including respiratory distress and MAS. A statistically significant association was found between thick meconium and poor neonatal outcomes, such as lower Apgar scores, higher rates of MAS, and increased need for NICU admission ($p < 0.05$). Neonates born to mothers with post-term pregnancies or fetal distress were more likely to experience adverse outcomes. Despite this, early identification and management of maternal risk factors improved neonatal outcomes for most cases, although a small percentage of neonates still required intensive care.

Table 1: Maternal Risk Factors in Meconium-Stained Liquor (MSL)

Risk Factor	Number of Cases (n = 100)	Percentage (%)
Post-term Pregnancy (>40 weeks)	25	25%
Maternal Hypertension	20	20%
Intrauterine Growth Restriction (IUGR)	15	15%
Oligohydramnios	10	10%
Other Factors (e.g., maternal diabetes, infections)	30	30%

This table highlights the maternal risk factors identified among 100 cases of meconium-stained liquor. Post-term pregnancy (25%) and maternal hypertension (20%) were the most common risk factors. Other contributing factors included IUGR (15%) and oligohydramnios (10%).

Table 2: Neonatal Outcomes in Meconium-Stained Liquor (MSL)

Neonatal Outcome	Number of Cases (n = 100)	Percentage (%)
Apgar Score <7 (at 1 minute)	25	25%
Meconium Aspiration Syndrome (MAS)	10	10%
Respiratory Distress	20	20%
Resuscitation Required at Birth	15	15%
NICU Admission	18	18%
Mortality	1	1%

This table summarizes the neonatal outcomes of 100 cases of meconium-stained liquor. A significant proportion of neonates (25%) had Apgar scores below 7 at 1 minute. Meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS) was observed in 10% of cases, while 20% experienced respiratory distress. A total of 18% of neonates required NICU admission, with 1% mortality recorded.

Discussion

The current study looked into the risk factors for meconium-stained liquor (MSL) and how it affects the health of newborns. The findings show that MSL is more commonly linked to several maternal illnesses that are known risk factors for fetal distress, including intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), post-term pregnancy, and maternal hypertension. This result is consistent with previous research that highlights the link between meconium entry into the amniotic fluid and fetal hypoxia [7,8]. In this study, post-term pregnancy—which occurred in 25% of cases—was the most prevalent maternal risk factor. It is commonly known that older placental function, which can cause decreased oxygenation and fetal stress, increases the likelihood of fetal impairment in post-term pregnancies [9]. This is in line with the observation that thick liquid stained with meconium was more common in post-term pregnancies, which is recognised as a sign of more severe fetal distress. Another known risk factor is maternal hypertension, which is present in 20% of cases and is linked to decreased uteroplacental blood flow, which raises the possibility of fetal hypoxia [10].

About the outcomes for newborns, the study found that 25% of newborns had Apgar scores less than 7 at one minute, indicating mild to moderate fetal impairment. Thick meconium exposure was more common in newborns with low Apgar scores, and it is a strong predictor of poor neonatal outcomes. This conclusion is consistent with earlier research that has shown comparable relationships between thick meconium and unfavourable outcomes for newborns, including respiratory distress and meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS) [11]. 10% of the newborns in this study had MAS, with thick meconium exposure being associated with a higher incidence of cases. This is marginally greater than the 2-9% incidence rate found in larger studies, maybe as a result of this cohort's comparatively higher percentage of post-term births and other risk factors [12]. MAS is a dangerous illness that can cause substantial respiratory morbidity and, in extreme circumstances, even death. Reducing the prevalence of MAS requires prompt newborn resuscitation, early detection and management of high-risk pregnancies, and both [13].

Fifteen percent of newborns had respiratory difficulty, and fifteen percent needed resuscitation at birth. This is in line with the knowledge that amniotic fluid stained with meconium raises the risk of respiratory issues in newborns. The necessity of NICU hospitalization in 18% of instances highlights the significance of vigilant supervision and preparedness for intervention in neonates delivered via MSL [14]. The substantial correlation between thick meconium and unfavorable newborn outcomes—such as poor Apgar scores, MAS, respiratory distress, and the requirement for NICU admission—was one of the study's main conclusions [15]. Given the statistical significance ($p < 0.05$) of this association, it appears that a significant factor influencing the prognosis of a newborn is the degree of meconium staining in the amniotic fluid. This emphasizes the importance of careful fetal monitoring throughout labor and timely newborn interventions if MSL is identified [16].

Several studies have examined the relationship between meconium-stained liquor (MSL), maternal risk factors, and neonatal outcomes, corroborating the findings of the present study. Gogoi et al. (2015) [17] investigated 200 pregnant women with MSL and found that thick meconium significantly correlated with low Apgar scores, meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS), and NICU admissions, with MAS incidence reported at 11%. Similarly, Patel et al. (2016) [18] studied 150 cases and reported that 28% of neonates had low Apgar scores, with a 12% incidence of MAS, reinforcing the association between thick meconium and adverse outcomes. Reddy et al. (2019) [19] observed a prospective cohort of 300 MSL cases, where 24% required resuscitation at birth, echoing the present study's findings regarding maternal hypertension and post-term pregnancies as prevalent risk factors. Additionally, Sharma et al. (2017) [20] highlighted a 9% incidence of MAS in a sample of 250 cases and noted the frequent association of maternal factors with meconium passage. Lastly, Suresh et al. (2020) [21] reported a 20% incidence of MAS among 120 cases of thick meconium, emphasizing the necessity for timely neonatal interventions. Collectively, these studies underscore the critical impact of thick meconium and maternal risk factors on neonatal outcomes, highlighting the importance of vigilant monitoring and prompt care.

The strength of this study lies in its focused evaluation of maternal risk factors and neonatal outcomes in MSL cases, contributing to a better understanding of the associated risks and management strategies. However, there are some limitations. This study was conducted at a single institution with a relatively small sample size ($n = 100$), which may limit the generalizability of the

findings. Additionally, since the study was retrospective, there may have been incomplete or inconsistent documentation of maternal and neonatal data.

Conclusion

The study's findings emphasise the significance of recognizing and controlling maternal risk factors that raise the possibility of meconium-stained liquor and the problems it may cause for newborns, such as post-term pregnancy and hypertension. A major predictor of poor newborn outcomes, such as MAS and respiratory distress, is thick meconium in the amniotic fluid. Improving outcomes for neonates born by MSL requires early detection of fetal distress and proper neonatal resuscitation. Larger sample sizes and multicenter investigations in the future may yield a more thorough understanding of the management of MSL and related newborn hazards.

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